

Screening of soil bacteria for in vitro degradation of endosulfan

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ABSTRACT

Endosulfan has been released to the environment mainly as a result of its use as an insecticide in crops and vegetable farms. Various microbial organisms are found to degrade toxic endosulfan to nontoxic endodiol. In present investigation the endosulfan contaminated soil sample around Nashik region were collected and screen for the presence of bacterial culture capable of degrading endosulfan. Three bacterial strains were isolated in the laboratory, where they use endosulfan as the sole source of sulfur and carbon in broth culture. No microbial growth was observed in absence of endosulfan. Change in pH of culture from neutral to acidic range supported the biological transformation. TLC analyses are used to reveal the formation of various intermediate of endosulfan metabolism. The metabolites formed indicate that the organism follows an oxidative pathway for metabolism of this pesticide. Microbial degradation of endosulfan by soil bacteria may provide a basis for the development of bioremediation strategies to remediate the pollutants in the environment.

INTRODUCTION

Endosulfan (6,7,8,9,10- hexachloro-1,5,5a,6,9,9a-hexahydro-6,9, methano-2,3,4-benzo-dioxathiopin-3-oxide) is a cyclodiene organochlorine currently used as an insecticide all over the India, as it possesses relatively broad spectrum of activity. It is used extensively throughout the country including Maharashtra, as contact and stomach insecticide on field crop, paddy, sorghum, oilseeds, vegetables, and fruit crops (Lee et al 1995, Kullman and Matsumura 1996). This results in frequent increase of soil contamination by pesticidal residue (Masood and Hassan 1995). Its

persistence in soil and aquatic environments has been widely reported by different researchers under different conditions (Rao and Murty 1980, Sethunathan et al 2002). It is extremely toxic to aquatic animals (Sing and Pandey 1990). It has also been reported for mammalian toxicity (Paul and Balasubramanian 1997, Chaudhuri et al 1999). These health and environmental concern has lead to study the source of detoxification and degradation of endosulfan. A variety of soil microorganisms have been reported to degrade endosulfan, although to different degree. Complete mineralization of the compound is reported by partial degradation into endosulfan sulfate and endodiol is more commonly observed (Sutherland et al 2002, Siddique et al 2003).

Present study involves screening and isolation of bacterial culture capable of metabolizing endosulfan from agricultural field areas of Nashik region, Maharashtra, India, with a history of endosulfan use for last 5-7 years.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Technical grade endosulfan 35 % preparation (Excel Industries Ltd, Mumbai, India) was used in all experiments. Standard endosulfate and endosulfan-diol were obtained from Sigma Aldrich. All other reagents were of high purity and analytical grade. The working solutions of these compounds were prepared by appropriate dilution of stock solution using acetone and hexane.

Four soil samples collected from Nashik region having a history of repeated endosulfan applications were used in this screening study for the isolation of endosulfan degrading microorganisms (Table1). The collected samples were stored at 40C. Microbial inoculum for the enrichment studies were prepared by shaking 20 gm of sample overnight in 100ml nutrient culture medium at 250C and 160 rpm. The solid particles were allowed to settle for one hour and aliquots of the supernatant were used to inoculate the nutrient culture media. The NSM (Non sulfur medium) and FTW medium (Herman and Frankenberg 1999) were prepared to assess the endosulfan as a sulfur and carbon source, respectively, for microbes in the enrichment study. The NSM and FTW were prepared as given by Siddique (2003). The pH was adjusted to 7.2. Erlenmeyer flask (50 ml) and nutrient culture media were separately autoclaved for 20 min at 1210C. 50mg/l Endosulfan was added in 9ml of FTW and

NSM culture media flasks. Then 1 ml of supernatant solution from the source flasks was added to inoculate the spiked flasks. One uninoculated flask was kept as control to compensate for any chemical degradation. These flasks were incubated on orbital shaker (160rpm) at 30°C for 15 days. There after subculture was maintained with 50mg l⁻¹ endosulfan on FTW and NSM media (Siddique et al 2003).

Isolation and purification of endosulfan degrading bacterial strains:

To isolate pure culture of bacterial strains, 0.1ml of enrichment culture (2nd time enriched) were centrifuged (8000rpm, 10min) with a microfuge. The supernatant was removed and pellets were resuspended in 0.05ml of sterile FTW and NSM nutrient media respectively by vortexing. These suspensions were plated on FTW endosulfan and NSM endosulfan agar media by streak plate techniques. The solid media were prepared by adding 2% washed agar in liquid FTW and NSM media, followed by autoclaving (121°C for 15 Min) after cooling the media 50°C, endosulfan was added aseptically (100mg l⁻¹) Enrichment agar plates were incubated at 30°C and discrete colonies were isolated. Isolates were further purified by streaking on fresh plates.

Screening of isolates for endosulfan degradation:

One bacterial strain exhibiting luxury growth on FTW endosulfan agar and two bacterial strains on NSM endosulfan agar were selected. The bacterial isolates were grown in respective nutrient culture medium having 100mg l⁻¹ Endosulfan for one week at 30°C and 160 rpm. The aliquots of these purified bacterial cultures were used for further studies. Endosulfan was dissolved in acetone and 100ul acetone was used to spike 100ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml of nutrient culture medium to give a final concentration of 100mg endosulfan l⁻¹. Inocula (2ml) were added to each spiked flask except control flask. Three flasks were kept without spiking endosulfan to check the growth of bacterial strains in absence of endosulfan. The flasks were incubated at 30°C, 160 rpm for 15 days. The pH of all culture flasks was measured at 24 h interval to assess the relationship between growth and metabolic activities of the microorganisms. This study was performed in triplicates.

Analytical procedure

Residual endosulfan in culture was extracted by addition of equal volume of acetone and shaken for one hour with a reciprocating shaker at 150 rpm and 300C (Siddique et al 2003). The acetone fractions from each flask were pooled and aliquots were analysed by TLC plates using Petroleum ether: acetone (85:15) solvent system. Spots were visualized by silver nitrate chromatogenic reagent and UV light. (Sutherland 2000).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In present study, the soil bacterial population was enriched for organism capable of degrading endosulfan. Bacterial soil sample (Table 1) were consecutively subculture in FTW and NSM broth containing endosulfan as sole source of carbon and sulfur respectively. Successful enrichment was observed by increased cell density in CH1 (FTW) and CH2, CUS (NSM) contain 50mg l⁻¹ endosulfan (Fig. 1) where as it is found very less and non significant in other samples in FTW and NSM medium.

Table 1. Source of environmental soil samples

S. No	Sample Code	Sample description	Area of collection
1	CH1	Horticulture (Grapes) field	Chansi, Nashik (M.S) India.
2	CH2	Wheat and Vegetable growing field	Chansi, Nashik (M.S) India.
3	CUS1	Sugarcane growing field	Chansi, Nashik (M.S) India.
4	SH	Tomato growing field	Gangapure, Nashik (M.S) India.

Figure 1. Growth of Mixed microbial culture in FTW and NSM medium containing 50mg/l endosulfan

Fig. 2. Change in pH of medium during the degradation of endosulfan by mixed microbial cultures. Values are average of three repeats

Thus these bacterial strains were selected for further study. Sutherland (2000) has reported endosulfan as a poor source of energy as it contains only six potential reducing electrons. Previous attempts for enrichment of endosulfan degrading microorganisms using insecticides as a carbon source have been unsuccessful (Guerin 1999). However, endosulfan has a relatively reactive cyclic sulfite diester group. In this study higher bacterial density was found in sample of CH2 and CUS from NSM and CH1 from FTW media (Fig. 1). Some authors have concluded the use of endosulfan as a source of carbon by bacterial cell for construction of cell components as well as to obtain energy (Alexander 1998, Sutherland 2002, Okeke 2002,).

The pH of culture media was measured during the incubation period of 15 days at 24 hrs intervals of CH1 in FTW, CH2, and CUS in NSM containing 100mg/l endosulfan. The pH was found to decrease in all three broth cultures. At the end of incubation the pH of culture media showed increased acidity up to pH 3.0 (Fig 2). This pH reduction in the culture medium may either be due to the dehalogenation of endosulfan resulting in the formation of HCl or organic acids produced by microorganism during their metabolic activities (Siddique et al 2003), while some authors reported the increased pH of growth medium during endosulfan degradation where they suggested the chemical degradation. Thus in present study decreased pH suggests increased biological degradation of endosulfan. (Martens 1976, Miles and Moy 1979)

The bacterial culture degrades endosulfan to produce various metabolites that can be detected by TLC. In present study the TLC of standard synthetic metabolites of endosulfan like, endosulfan diol and endosulfan sulfate were used to compare the endosulfan degradation product. TLC of standard sample gives four spots with lowest Rf value of Endosulfan diol, then Endosulfan sulfate, and highest Rf values of \hat{a} and \acute{a} endosulfan, Where as in uninoculated sample, only two spots of \hat{a} and \acute{a} endosulfan were visible (Table 2). In CH1 CH2 and CUS sample only two spots were visible; there Rf value is correspond to the standard endosulfan sulphate

and endosulfan diol. Degradation of endosulfan with production of metabolites Endosulfan sulfate, endosulfan diol was similar to that in earlier reports (Martens 1976, Shetty et al 2000, Sutherland et al 2002, Kwon et al 2002, Lee et al 2003, Mukherjee and Mittal 2005). Formation of endosulfan sulfate and endosulfan diol supported the presence of oxidative and hydrolytic enzymatic activities. (Kullman and Matsumura 1996, Sutherland et al 2000, Lee et al 2003). A change in pH of medium to acidic in present study suggests the microbial degradation of endosulfan. Increasing pH may favor chemical transformation of endosulfan to endosulfan diol. No rise in pH in present study suggests that endodiol formation is due to biological hydrolysis and not by chemical hydrolysis (Martens 1976).

Table 2: Rf values, using thin layer chromatography of standard, un inoculated and sample broths.

Sample	No of spots observed	Rf values
Standard (mixture of Endosulfan sulfate, and endosulfan diol)	Two	0.14 (endosulfan diol) 0.39 (endosulfan sulfate)
Uninoculated endosulfan sample	Two	0.72 (Alfa Endosulfan) 0.62 (beta endosulfan)
CH1	Two	0.14 (match to endosulfan diol) 0.39 (match to endosulfan sulfate)
CH2	Two	0.14 (match to endosulfan diol) 0.39 (match to endosulfan sulfate)
CUS	Two	0.14 (match to endosulfan diol) 0.39 (match to endosulfan sulfate)

In conclusion we have successfully enriched and isolated hyper active endosulfan degrading bacterial strains from the fertile agriculture soil of Nashik region that utilizes endosulfan as a carbon or sulfur source. These results have valuable application for endosulfan bioremediation in polluted sites. We are currently attempting to select a pure bacterium from the mixed culture that is capable of

degrading endosulfan. Such a bacterium would potentially be a valuable source of catalytic enzymes for the development of bioremediating agent to reduce endosulfan residue problems in run-off irrigation waters.

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